

Machine learning in Metabolomics

Daniel Aumayr
University of Applied Sciences Kufstein, Tirol
Kufstein, Austria

Figure 1: workflow untargeted metabolomic studies [1]

ABSTRACT

Machine learning is a crucial and growing element in the field of biochemistry. Recent publications as AlphaFold for predictions of protein folding made a big impact in the scientific community. This paper is looking at the advancements on a step deeper down the line where molecules are analysed. In the field of metabolomic studies, especially mass spectrometry analysis some new procedures using machine learning where introduced. Recent solutions are reviewed, limitations and future research fields are identified.

KEYWORDS

Metabolomics, machine learning, Spectral similarity measure, Mass spectrometry

1 INTRODUCTION

Plants consist of a wide variety of compounds. Many of these are secondary metabolites and include aromatic substances, most of which are phenols or their oxygen-substituted derivatives such as tannins[4].

Microbial secondary metabolites are small molecular products of secondary metabolism that are usually formed in the late growth phase (idiophase) of microorganisms. They have an unusual structure and are produced from intracellular mediators (amino acids, sugars, fatty acids, etc.) that are condensed into more complex structures by specific biochemical pathways. They are not essential for the growth of productive crops, but perform various survival

functions in nature. They are very important for human health and economy in our society. These include antibiotics, antitumor agents, cholesterol-lowering drugs, immunosuppressants, anthelmintics and other parasiticides, herbicides, ruminant growth stimulants, agricultural fungicides, bioinsecticides and others[9].

Many of these compounds have antioxidant properties. This discovery has demonstrated that plant medicines can be purified and administered in precise dosages, regardless of the source or age of the material. With this continuing trend, products from plants and natural sources, or analogs inspired by them, have contributed greatly to today's commercial drug preparations. Of the 177 drugs approved worldwide for the treatment of cancer, more than 70% are based on natural products or mimetics, many of which have been improved by combinatorial chemistry[12].

Mass spectrometry (MS) is one of the commonly used tools to identify the compounds in the plant extracts. MS is an analytical tool for measuring the mass-to-charge ratio (m/z) of the molecules present in a sample. These measurements can often be used to calculate the exact molecular weight of a compound. However, having thousands of compounds in each extract, it poses a challenge to interpret the MS data[11].

In this paper will introduce some of the basic analytical methods in metabolomics and take a closer look at the state of the art approaches in the recent years analysing molecules for medicine.

2 BACKGROUND

There are two approaches in metabolomic studies. The targeted approach refers to a method in which a specified metabolites are measured, typically focusing on one or multiple related pathways of interest. The untargeted approach tries to measure as many metabolites as possible at once[8].

Untargeted metabolomic studies are an important tool to analyse metabolites, which are small molecules involved in cellular reactions such as antioxidants. Those studies measure a large number of metabolites at once and produce large amounts of complex data. In Figure 1 a pipeline of an untargeted metabolomic study is shown. Spectral data of the biological samples is generated via nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), liquid chromatography or gas chromatography (GC) followed by mass spectrometry technologies. The data will be analysed using univariate and multivariate methods to find certain biomarkers or the individual metabolites can be identified using spectral databases. In the last step a biological interpretation can be created to get further information about the interactions of the metabolites[1].

The field of application for machine learning and data science in this area is broad. In the next section we take a closer look at the spectral processing and metabolite identification and the advancements of machine learning in this fields.

3 METHODS

Identification of these compounds relies on tandem MS data obtained by fragmenting the compound and recording the masses of the fragments. In contrast, molecular structure databases such as PubChem and ChemSpider contain millions of compounds, with PubChem alone having more than 50 million entries. Searching molecular structure databases using MS/MS data is therefore considered a powerful tool to assist an expert in elucidating a compound. Particular progress has been made with limited metabolite classes such as lipids and peptides, the results cannot be generalised to other metabolite classes[2].

For the general case, several strategies have been proposed a few years back, including simulation of mass spectra based on molecular structure, combinatorial fragmentation, and molecular fingerprint prediction[2].

In the last few years machine learning, especially deep learning, took a bigger role in this field and approaches to predict the molecular fingerprint from mass spectra[5].

In 2020 the DeepEI method was introduced which predicts the fingerprint of the MS Spectrum with an artificial neural network and searches molecular structure databases with this fingerprint. As shown in Figure 2 the neural network is trained using spectra from databases. The NIST 2017 was used for training and the Spectra from MassBank were used for the evaluation. When a new spectra needs to be identified a fingerprint will be predicted and structure databases will be searched for fitting candidates and these candidates were extracted. The fingerprints of the candidates out of the database will be scored against the predicted fingerprint using the Jaccard similarity score.[6]

MetFID was also introduced in 2020 which has a similar workflow as the DeepEI. In Figure 3 the introduced artificial neural network is shown. It consists of two fully connected hidden layers with

Figure 2: Workflow DeepEI. [6].

Figure 3: MetFID artificial neural network architecture. [3].

800 and 600 neurons. The activation function for the hidden layers is the rectified linear unit. Between the last hidden layer and the fingerprint layer the softmax activation function is used. For the training the 'adam' optimiser and categorical cross-entropy loss function were used. The model was trained for 30 epochs with a batch size of 100[3].

One of the biggest obstacles in predicting molecular fingerprints is that they are usually large, very sparse binary vectors. Less frequent structural features are difficult to predict correctly with limited training data. As a result, the above mentioned deep learning approaches focused only on predicting frequently activated patches of molecular fingerprints[5].

Current open spectrum libraries grow to such a large extent that machine learning methods have sufficient data for training deep neural networks. This may be an opportunity to develop alternative mass spectral similarity scores. This is also consistent with a recent review article describing the current and future role of deep learning in metabolite annotation[7].

In 2021 the MS2DeepScore was introduced which uses a Siamese neural network to predict the similarity between spectra without additional metadata or library information. It is a very fast and scalable tool for large-scale comparisons and analyses of spectra with unknown compounds[5].

As shown in Figure 4 a Siamese network uses the same network twice during training and prediction to transform the associated

Figure 4: MS2DeepScore Siamese neural network architecture. [5].

spectrum into a spectral embedding. The network is trained on the mean square error between the spectral pairs and the cosine similarity of the two spectral embedding and the true structural similarity score. Data imputation techniques including moderate random changes in peak intensity and removal and addition of low-intensity peaks were used to increase model reliability[5].

4 LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

As above mentioned the performance of the first two approaches is limited due to the fact that the data is very large and the computational time predicting every possibility or training a neural network with all molecules in a database is very expensive[3, 5].

All three approaches have the problem of explainability in common. When training neural networks this is often a limitation, because it is not deterministic what exactly happens in the network. There are different approaches to handle this limitation as Monte-Carlo Dropout or explainability tools as 'shapley'[5].

Figure 5: MS2DeepScore example cluster. [5].

Another limitation especially for the MS2DeepScore approach is the clustering. As shown in Figure 5 it is possible to cluster the predicted molecules. Although some molecules are quite scattered. This is due to the fact that molecules can have sugars attached to them changing the form of the molecule. There is a sugar removal tool, which will remove the sugar components out of the data[10].

This will increase again the computational time and may be improved in future work to train a Siamese neural network that can fade out the sugar automatically.

5 CONCLUSION

As shown in this paper machine learning has held entry into the field of biochemistry for quite some time. New approaches are developed which automate certain tasks and increase the efficiency of the work in the field. We took a closer look at a small portion of the field and reviewed current approaches in the area of mass spectrometry analysis.

The current approaches look very promising and with further research and refinement some of the limitations may be eliminated.

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